

Procedure			Source	Stochastic processes because of fluctuating core quality	Explanation	Arbitrary failure rates of cores	Explanation	Challenges	Variable processing times	Explanation	Technical incompatibilities causing variable transition times	Explanation
Heuristic	Forward Scheduling	Wendahl (2019) 978-3-446-44661-8	1	Forward scheduling requires a fixed work plan (fixed number of operations) in advance. If it only becomes clear during processing (e.g. after step 2) that an additional step (welding) is necessary, the originally calculated end date becomes invalid. The method has no mechanism for 'unplanned paths'.	1	Forward scheduling calculates the order hourly. If a core fails in step 1 (reject), the run ends there in reality. The process itself does not 'notice' this and schedules fictitious capacities for the subsequent steps until the order is cancelled manually.	2	Rigid buffering is necessary. Forward scheduling uses fixed planned times from the master data. In order to cushion the variance (e.g. run removal takes 10-30 minutes), the master data must be inflated with extremely high safety margins (buffers). If you plan using worst-case times, the delivery date is artificially pushed for into the future (high planned lead time), even though the order could often be completed much faster. This leads to unnecessarily high inventories. → According to Lidding, this also leads to poor adherence to delivery dates.	1	Ignoring blockages. If a part is held up due to a lack of spare parts or clarification requirements, the transition time explodes. Forward scheduling only adds the planned transition time.		
	Backward Scheduling	Wendahl (2019) 978-3-446-44661-8	1	Backward scheduling is based on a fixed work plan. If an additional step (welding) is required in remanufacturing with a probability of 30%, the deterministic model ignores this time requirement. The calculated start date is too late. If the additional step occurs, the delivery date can no longer be met because there is no buffer ('slack').	1	Backward scheduling plans for one order. If the core fails in the middle of the process (at step 3), the order is 'lost'. A new order would have to be started immediately. Since backward scheduling plans 'to the edge' (latest start), there is no time left to bring in a replacement core. The delivery date is immediately missed. Li et al. (2015) argue that random yields necessarily require buffer stocks or earlier start times, which contradicts the 'just-in-time' logic of backward scheduling. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cir.2014.01.005	2	To be on the safe side, companies often use 'safety lead times' (buffers) for backward scheduling. In remanufacturing, however, the variance (standard deviation) is so high that the buffers would have to be enormous. The calculated start date often slips into the past ('We should have started last week'). The system generates unrealistic 'rush orders' even before the work begins.	1	Backward scheduling assumes 'smooth' transitions. If a part is awaiting clarification (incompatibility), the process comes to a standstill.		
	Midpoint Scheduling	Wendahl (2019) 978-3-446-44661-8	1	In remanufacturing, it is not clear which work step will become the bottleneck. Cleaning may be the bottleneck for 70% of cores, but for 30% of poor-quality cores, corrosion protection coating is the bottleneck. The 'third' bottleneck is incurred. The plan is disrupted by unforeseen bottlenecks (at other stations). A classic example from the literature: Diagnosis is set as the bottleneck, but 10% of the cores require a completely different route instead of diagnosis → replacement.	1	Centralized scheduling attempts to utilize the bottleneck to 100% capacity ('constraint exploitation'). However, if 30% of the cores fail and leave the bottleneck earlier, capacity suddenly becomes available (it is not being used). The system cannot respond flexibly. The upstream machines are inhibited (because they are waiting for the bottleneck), while the downstream machines are started (because fewer finished parts are coming in).	1	If an upstream operation takes longer than planned (extra part + extra grinding, arrival at the bottleneck is delayed). This results in underutilization of the bottleneck. The plan, which was based on bottleneck utilization, becomes invalid. A new bottleneck arises upstream. The entire schedule is obsolete.	1	If a part remains pending clarification (e.g. question: 'Is this material compatible?'), the supply to the bottleneck and later the output from the bottleneck will back up. Blockage of the system ("starvation" upstream, "blocking" downstream).		
	Two-Phase Heuristic for Disassembly Scheduling	Kim et al. (2007) https://doi.org/10.1080/00207179020844443 https://doi.org/10.1215/095495940304049	2	Only indirectly takes into account. The model works with fixed parts lists and fixed disassembly plans, commonly (shared parts) taken into account, but not the fact that individual cores require additional or alternative steps.	1	If an item only based on conservatively assumed planned quantities. Kim et al. model the disassembly quantities deterministically. Random scrap rates are not explicitly represented stochastically.	1	Not addressed at all. Disassembly times are deterministic parameters; the heuristic optimizes across quantities and sequences, not across distributed times.	1	Later work (e.g. capacitated disassembly scheduling under stochastic yield) shows that real yield uncertainty leads to significant cost effects that are not reflected in a deterministic heuristic such as Kim's Two-Phase. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2017.08.032	1	Not explicitly taken into account. The model assumes that all planned disassembly steps are technically feasible and can be carried out immediately. Additional, stochastic waiting times are not modeled. The heuristic therefore systematically produces overly optimistic throughput times.
	Shifting Bottleneck Heuristic	Yu & Lee (2016) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.swevo.2016.04.048	3	Different representing routes and machine selection are represented in the model (flexible job shop). The stochastic nature of the routes (i.e. the fact that it is only clear after diagnosis whether route 1 or route 2 is necessary) is not modeled dynamically. The model works with routes that are known a priori.	1	The paper assumes deterministic quantities of returning cores and solves the matching problem between recovered components and remanufactured products.	1	Yu & Lee work with deterministic processing times per machine and work step, as is customary in classic scheduling literature. Typical random dispersion (e.g. 'slightly dirty' vs. 'heavily corroded') is not modeled probabilistically.	3	This is precisely where heuristics come into their strength: they model component matching requirements – certain components may only be combined with certain product instances. This is a form of technical incompatibility that is covered by the mathematical model as constraints. (Unplanned, situational incompatibilities (e.g. classification cases in quality management, missing documentation) are not modeled. The model perfectly masters 'planned incompatibility' (this part MUST go with that housing through its family logic. However, it is blind to 'unplanned incompatibilities' (this part CAN SURELY NOT be used, as it assumes perfect, trouble-free execution of each plan step).		
Meta-Heuristic	Integrated scheduling for remanufacturing system considering component commonality	Guo et al. (2023) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cir.2023.109419	3	The model explicitly maps several stages (disassembly, reprocessing, reassembly) and routing alternatives via commonality (parts can be reused in different products). The route logic is parameterized deterministically; quality-related additional steps or dynamic route changes during execution are not modeled as random variables, but via fixed process plans.	1	The authors focus on the size of already reprocessed components and commonality, not on scrap probabilities or complete core failure. Random yield is taken into account at most implicitly via conservative resource/part availability assumptions; true yield stochasticity remains unmodeled.	1	Processing times are used as deterministic parameters; multi-criteria optimization (makespan, energy) makes the plan robust against peak loads, but not against explicit stochasticity.	4	The paper explicitly addresses component commonality and matching – i.e. which parts are compatible with which products. These technical compatibility conditions are firmly anchored in the model and are respected by the CA. Situational incompatibilities (e.g. external approvals, detailed problems with individual cores) can only be mapped if they are known in advance as model restrictions.		
	Optimization of remanufacturing flexible job shop scheduling	Chen & Gao (2020) 10.25236/AEES.2020.030009	1	The problem is a flexible job shop – alternative machines for each operation, but the sequence of operations per job is fixed. Machine flexibility is modeled, but routes stochastic in the sense of additional or alternative process steps (e.g. extra repair after diagnosis) are not part of the model.	1	The number of orders is considered a given; random yield or failure of individual cores is not explicitly treated as a random variable.	4	Uncertain processing times are modeled using triangular and trapezoidal fuzzy numbers; the GA optimizes based on these fuzzy operation times and fuzzy due dates.	3	Machine capabilities and, if applicable, setups are taken into account as constraints; M50S (Machine Selection and Operation Sequence) coding ensures that only permissible machines/operations are selected. Specific remain incompatibilities (e.g. only certain cores with certain tools) can only be mapped if they are programmed into these constraints; spontaneous/unclear transition issues are not taken into account.		
	Scheduling in a three-stage remanufacturing system with machine blockage, deterioration and maintenance	Luo et al. (2025) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.swevo.2025.102185	2	The model depicts a three-stage structure (disassembly – reprocessing – reassembly), within the stages, blockage and maintenance effects are used, alternative process routes.	1	The work focuses on machine status (blockages, deterioration, RMAI) and treats cores more as deterministic jobs.	4	A deterioration model is presented in which processing times become longer over time as the machines wear out; rate-modifying activities (RMA, i.e. type of maintenance) shorten the time again. The model explicitly depicts a realistic, time-dependent variance component of processing times; the metaheuristic (MMBO) optimizes start times and maintenance times simultaneously in order to minimize the makespan in the event of blockage and wear.	3	Primarily via blockage models (limited buffers, blocking downstream stages) and maintenance constraints. Transition problems resulting from buffer restrictions and maintenance (e.g. parts cannot be transported further) are explicitly mapped. Other technical incompatibilities (special tools, approvals) are also only taken into account here if they are formulated as constraints in the model.		
Deterministic / optimal Deterministische Optimierung (LP / MILP)	More mixed integer linear programming models	Wang et al. (2024) 10.1016/j.cir.2024.110379	1	Wang et al. develop MILP models for a deterministic three-stage scheduling problem (Disassembly-Reprocessing-Reassembly). The models assume fixed process routes and do not account for the fact that varying core conditions lead to different routing decisions. Stochasticity within the routes themselves is not part of the model.	1	Wang et al. develop MILP models for a deterministic three-stage scheduling problem (Disassembly-Reprocessing-Reassembly). The models assume fixed process routes and do not account for the fact that varying core conditions lead to different routing decisions. Stochasticity within the routes themselves is not part of the model.	2	MILP models for scheduling can theoretically capture variable processing times in the parameters (e.g. different disassembly/reprocessing/reassembly times per job). However, it is unclear whether Wang et al. explicitly work with stochastic or variable times or whether processing times are deterministic. The focus lies on the scheduling problem itself, not on modeling the root causes of variability (core quality, unexpected damage).	1	The model focuses on temporal planning of three standardized process steps and does not address technical incompatibilities between components, design variants, or alternative procurement paths that would result in variable transition times.		
	Batch production scheduling problem in a reconfigurable hybrid manufacturing remanufacturing system	Vahedi-Nouri et al. (2025) 10.1016/j.cir.2025.111999	1	Vahedi-Nouri et al. focus on batch production scheduling in a Hybrid Manufacturing Remanufacturing System (HMRS) with reconfigurable machines. The study develops MILP and CP models for scheduling HDL products alongside new manufacturing, but does not model stochastic or quality-dependent process routes. The problem formulation assumes that products follow predefined routes without considering how varying core conditions lead to different routing decisions.	1	The paper addresses scheduling optimization in an HMRS context but does not explicitly model uncertainty in core failure rates or remanufacturability. While the motivation mentions HDL products, the scheduling model treats jobs deterministically without incorporating random failure probabilities or variable remanufacturability levels of individual cores.	2	The batch scheduling model on non-identical parallel reconfigurable machines can theoretically accommodate different processing times per job or batch. However, the paper does not explicitly address variable processing times driven by core quality uncertainty or unexpected damage during remanufacturing operations. The focus is on deterministic scheduling optimization rather than modeling the root causes of processing time variability in remanufacturing contexts.	2	The study explicitly considers 'non-identical parallel reconfigurable machines' and batch grouping, which implies consideration of machine-specific capabilities and setup requirements. Reconfigurable Manufacturing Systems (RMS) are designed to provide customized production capabilities and flexibility, which may indirectly relate to handling different product variants. However, the paper does not explicitly model technical incompatibilities between components, design variants, or variable transition times caused by engineering clarifications or part substitutions.		
	A capacitated disassembly scheduling problem considering processing technology selection and parts commonality	Dargbouth and Abdel-Aal (2021) 10.1007/s12343-021-00104-3	2	Dargbouth and Abdel-Aal (2021) address a capacitated disassembly scheduling problem considering processing technology selection and parts commonality. The inclusion of 'processing technology selection' suggests that different cores or components may require different processing paths or technologies, which indirectly relates to quality-dependent routing. However, the paper does not explicitly model stochastic or quality-driven process routes where the routing decision is a random outcome based on inspected core conditions. The technology selection appears to be a deterministic optimization decision rather than a stochastic routing outcome driven by fluctuating core quality.	4	The paper explicitly considers stochastic yield in the disassembly process, which directly relates to uncertainty in core failure and component recoverability. Related work by the same authors on 'Capacitated disassembly scheduling under stochastic yield' indicates that yield uncertainty – the unpredictable proportion of usable components retrieved from disassembly – is a central concern. This aligns with 'arbitrary failure rates,' as yield variability reflects the fact that not all cores yield the same number of reusable parts due to varying degradation and failure patterns. However, the formulation typically treats yield as a probabilistic parameter rather than explicitly modeling individual core failure mechanisms.	2	The paper focuses on capacitated disassembly scheduling, which inherently requires modeling of processing times to determine feasible schedules. Variable processing times driven by core condition variability are a common feature in disassembly scheduling literature. However, it is unclear from the available abstract and citations whether Dargbouth and Abdel-Aal (2021) explicitly model stochastic or variable processing times, or whether they treat processing times as deterministic parameters. The related work on 'Capacitated disassembly scheduling with random demand and operation time' suggests that variable operation times are addressed in the broader research program, but specific treatment in this 2021 paper requires verification.	1	The paper explicitly considers parts commonality, which relates to the fact that multiple end-of-life product types may share common components. This consideration implicitly acknowledges that different product variants, design versions, or generations may have compatibility issues during disassembly and reassembly. However, the paper does not explicitly model 'variable transition times' caused by technical incompatibilities, engineering clarifications, or part substitution requirements. The focus appears to be on optimizing disassembly scheduling given parts commonality, rather than modeling the time variability induced by incompatibility resolution.		
Stochastische / dynamische Optimierung	Stochastic dynamic programming	Lago Jumeir & Filho (2017) https://doi.org/10.1007/s10190-015-0420-1	5	Disassembly routing is explicitly part of the model: a core can run through different disassembly paths with different probabilities (e.g. depending on its state).	4	Random yield is linked to stochastic routes: certain routes end earlier (e.g. rejects) or deliver fewer parts. The heuristic recalibrates planning at each horizon roll based on the actual routes and quantities that occurred. Although the authors do not model 'real' failure rates, their mathematical approach (stochastic dynamic programming) is perfectly suited to integrating this change.	2	The primary work focuses on stochastic routes and quantities; processing times are assumed to be deterministic or fixed parameters. Variance in times is not modeled as a random variable, but would have to be incorporated into the parameters again via safety margins. At the period level, however, the rolling horizon concept has a dampening effect: overdue times in one period are 'forgiven' during the next replanning cycle.	1	The model focuses on disassembly decisions, not on all technical details of the reprocessing or assembly stage.		
	Stochastic model predictive control for remanufacturing system management	Li et al. (2021) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmep.2021.02.002	5	Li et al. (2021) propose a stochastic model predictive control (SMPC) approach for remanufacturing system management that explicitly considers 'high uncertainty in the product quality'. The paper addresses uncertainty in core quality as a central modeling challenge, which directly drives variability in process routing decisions. The stochastic control framework is designed to manage systems where incoming core quality varies significantly, leading to different remanufacturing paths.	3	The paper explicitly models 'high uncertainty in the product quality and system dynamics' in remanufacturing operations. While not framed specifically as 'arbitrary failure rates,' quality uncertainty in remanufacturing inherently incorporates variability in core failure states and remanufacturability. The stochastic model predictive control approach is designed to handle unpredictable core conditions, which implicitly includes varying failure rates. However, the paper does not explicitly model individual component failure probabilities as a separate parameter.	3	The SMPC approach is designed to manage 'remanufacturing system management' under uncertainty, and variable processing times are a natural consequence of quality variation in remanufacturing operations. The paper focuses on optimizing 'remanufacturing efficiency' in the presence of uncertainty, which typically requires modeling variable processing times. However, based on available abstracts, it is unclear whether variable processing times are explicitly modeled as stochastic parameters or emerge implicitly through the system dynamics model.	1	The paper focuses on stochastic control and quality uncertainty but does not explicitly address technical incompatibilities between components, design versions, or product generations. There is no indication that the model captures variable transition times caused by part incompatibilities, engineering clarifications, or component substitution requirements. The scope appears limited to quality-driven uncertainty rather than design-related compatibility issues.		
	Scheduling a Stochastic Remanufacturing Process with Disassembly, Reprocessing and Reassembly	Fu et al. (2020) 10.1019/CNSC4898.2020.9238106	3	Fu et al. (2020) address scheduling for 'a stochastic remanufacturing process including three subsystems, i.e., disassembly, reprocessing and reassembly.' The paper models routing decisions at the workstation level (i.e., which parallel disassembly or reassembly workstation a core is assigned to) under uncertainty. However, this is not fine-grained quality-dependent process routing within individual work systems. The model does not capture detailed in-process routing decisions such as: 'Does this core require cleaning → inspection → partial disassembly, or can it skip cleaning?' The stochasticity relates to workstation assignment and sequencing rather than detailed process step selection driven by inspected core quality. Therefore, while routing variability exists, it operates at a higher abstraction level than the detailed, quality-driven process routes characteristic of remanufacturing operations at the work-system level.	4	The paper models a 'stochastic multi-objective integrated disassembly' problem, and related work by the same research group explicitly addresses 'stochastic yield' in disassembly processes. While Fu et al. (2020) do not explicitly use the term 'failure rates,' the stochastic nature of the remanufacturing process inherently captures uncertainty in which cores and components are recoverable and usable. The three-stage structure (disassembly, reprocessing, reassembly) suggests consideration of yield variability, though explicit modeling of failure rates requires verification from the full paper.	3	The paper addresses 'Scheduling a Stochastic Remanufacturing Process,' and scheduling problems at the workstation level inherently require modeling of processing times. Variable or stochastic processing times are likely modeled for workstation operations (e.g., total time at a disassembly workstation). However, this likely does not capture the fine-grained variability driven by individual core conditions – such as unexpected damage requiring additional cleaning, rework loops, or unplanned inspection steps within a workstation. The processing time variability is probably captured as a stochastic parameter at the job/workstation level rather than modeled as dynamic, condition-dependent task sequences.	1	The paper focuses on scheduling optimization under stochastic conditions for the three-stage remanufacturing process (disassembly, reprocessing, reassembly). There is no indication that technical incompatibilities between components, design versions, or product generations are considered. The focus appears to be on operational uncertainty and scheduling efficiency rather than design-related compatibility issues or variable transition times caused by part substitution or engineering clarifications.		
AI-based	Deep reinforcement learning for real-time scheduling of collaborative customization remanufacturing	Yasavurparat et al. (2025) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rim.2025.102980	5	Mapped across the state space: quality type, necessary rework operations and intermediate buffers are state variables; the agent learns how different paths affect system utilization and future start times. Only the route variants stored in the simulation model are learned; completely new error patterns require retraining.	4	In the simulated environment, rejects and cancellations occur as events; the reward function is low or unfulfilled orders, so that the agent learns policies that select buffers and sequences in such a way that failure risks are cushioned in terms of timing. The policy is always limited to the learned yield distributions; significant changes in distribution lead to mistakes.	4	Variability in processing times (disruptions, rework) is part of the environment; the agent learns how different implementation shifts in planned end times and times, for example, to make more robust start decisions ('put on the edge'). There is an explicit model of distribution; robustness arises empirically through experience, not analytically.	3	Known incompatibilities (certain combinations of parts/machines, approvals) are coded in the MDP as impermissible actions or states; the agent then only generates technically permissible start time decisions. Spontaneous, unmodeled incompatibilities are not taken into account – human intervention is still required here.		
	Lead time prediction using machine learning algorithms	Lingtu et al. (2018) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2018.03.148	4	If routing variants (e.g. additional rework steps) are reflected in the input characteristics (product condition, process path), the model 'learns' their influence on the actual throughput time. The route itself is not optimized, only its time sequence; training data is missing for new or rare routes.	3	Failures are not typically included in the training as 'limited LT' predominantly successful runs are modeled. ML-LT prediction therefore primarily addresses time variance, not the probability that an order will fail completely.	3	The ML models implicitly integrate processing, waiting and downtime into the LT forecast and can also provide quantities (e.g. 80% percentiles) instead of a fixed value. For lead time scheduling, this means that start/end dates are based on data-driven, variability-sensitive LTs instead of rigid master data.	3	If certain combinations (material, machine, process variant) systematically lead to longer lead times and are coded in the features, the model captures this effect. Ad hoc incompatibilities that occur rarely are hardly learned due to the small number of cases. In addition, technical barriers are less likely to be picked up due to the simplification of the hardware side (capabilities of individual machines).		
	Reinforcement learning and digital twin-based real-time scheduling method in intelligent manufacturing systems	Zhang et al. (2022) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2022.09.413	4	The DT can model multiple paths and their probabilities; the DRL agent 'experiences' in the simulation how deliverable process choices lead to different end times. Modeling effort is high; new/unplanned routes do not initially exist in the DT.	5	Yield uncertainty can be explicitly mapped stochastically in the DT; the agent learns scheduling strategies that deliver acceptable adherence to deadlines despite rejects (e.g. earlier starts, parallel disassembly). Quality depends heavily on the calibration of the failure distributions in the DT.	5	DT models typically contain distribution-based process times; DRL learns policies that deal with this variance, e.g. by starting critical jobs early or loading certain machines differently. In contrast to purely data-driven DRL approaches, process engineers can explicitly control the time distributions in the DT.	5	DT/DRL addresses transition times and technical incompatibilities, provided these are encoded in the digital twin as sequence-, buffer- or state-dependent transition/setup times; the RL agent optimizes its start time decisions precisely against these (variable) transition dynamics.		